

Analyzing policy interactions for promoting energy efficiency in the Hellenic sectors of buildings and transport

by

Dr. Popi KONIDARI¹

Head of Climate Change Policy Unit of the Energy Policy and Development Centre (KEPA)

Mrs. Anna FLESSA, MSc.

Fellow Researcher of the KEPA

Mrs. Aliki-Nefeli MAVRAKI, MSc.

Fellow Researcher of the KEPA

Mrs. Eleni-Danai MAVRAKI, MSc.

Fellow Researcher of the KEPA

¹ *Contact details of corresponding author*

Tel: +30 210 72 75 732

Fax: +30 210 7275 732

e-mail: pkonidar@kepa.uoa.gr

Address: KEPA Building, Panepistimiopolis, 157 84, Athens, Greece

Abstract

Policy interactions are important parameters for the successful implementation of policies, measures and policy instruments. The parallel implementation of a number of policy instruments has the potential to create synergies or conflicts that maximize or prevent the achievement of their anticipated outcomes. This paper analyses three cases of policy interactions between two policy instruments for promoting even more the energy efficiency outcomes in Greece for two sectors, buildings and transport. The case studies refer to existing policy instruments linked directly and indirectly with energy and are: i) “Energy labelling” and “Green Public Procurement” (building and transport sector); ii) “Regulation for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings (KENAK)” and the “Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs” (only for building sector); iii) “Planning policy instrument for Intelligent Transport Systems” and “Emission standards (Euro 5 and Euro 6)” (only for transport sector). The analysis is conducted through four levels (objectives, target groups, rules-influencing mechanisms and implementation network). Within each level the policy interaction is examined of how it affects: i) the performance of each policy instrument and ii) the behavior of end-users. Conclusions discuss policy recommendations for improving the outcomes of each case study.

1. Introduction

Policy interactions contribute essentially to the successful parallel implementation of policies, measures and policy instruments since they have the potential to create synergies or conflicts that facilitate or prevent respectively the achievement of the anticipated outcomes. This paper presents cases of positive policy interactions between two Policy Instruments (PIs) for promoting even more the Energy Efficiency (EE) outcomes in Greece for two sectors, buildings and transport. The

case studies refer to existing PIs that are linked directly and indirectly with energy. There are no officially recorded outcomes or evaluations for the parallel implementation of these PIs. The paper is structured as follows: first, the types of policy interactions are presented. Then the case studies are described. The types of the policy interactions for the case studies are analysed. The last session is about conclusions and recommendations for improving the performance of the examined PIs based on the analysis of their policy interactions.

2. Policy interactions

Policy interaction is the situation that occurs when parallel-implemented PIs exert on each other multi-dimensional and multi-scaled interactions that end up either interfering and constraining or complementing and reinforcing performance mutually or separately (Konidari and Mavrakis, 2006).

Their identification and analysis is based on the design characteristics of PIs. These characteristics are classified in the following four categories (Mavrakis and Konidari, 2003): i) *Objectives* which are the set of explicitly mentioned and forecasted outcomes of the instrument. They are divided into primary and secondary. ii) *Target groups* which are entities that fall under the instrument and are obliged to comply with its requirements. iii) *Implementation network* that is the set of pertinent public and private authorities assigned with specific duties (diffusion of information, conduction of controls, etc.) for the successful implementation of the policy instrument. iv) *Rules and influencing mechanisms* that refer to all legal and financial arrangements used for compliance, coercion, encouragement and persuasion of target groups towards the fulfilment of objectives.

Based on these classification categories there are four respective forms (mentioned also as levels) of interactions each one of which is divided into others (Konidari and Mavrakis, 2006):

- i) *Interactions due to objectives*. Two PIs interact due to objectives if: a) They share the same primary objectives; this interaction form is named primary to primary (p-p). b) one primary objective is the same with a secondary objective; interaction form is named primary to secondary (p-s). c) They share the same secondary objectives; interaction form is secondary to secondary (s-s) (Konidari and Mavrakis, 2006).
- ii) *Interactions due to target groups*. These interactions occur when PIs are imposed at the same target groups or when operations of other sectors, linked with the specific target groups of the two examined instruments, are affected. The first form of interaction is named direct target group interaction, while the second indirect (i-i) (Konidari and Mavrakis,

2006). Using TP1 and TP2 to denote the set of target groups in policy instrument 1 and 2, respectively, three possible combinations for direct interaction occur as described by the following relationships. First, if $TP1 \subseteq TP2$ then $(TP1 \cap TP2) = TP1$ or if $TP2 \subseteq TP1$ then $(TP1 \cap TP2) = TP2$ (One Set PArticipation, os-pa). Second, if $TP1 \cap TP2 = TP3$ and $TP3 \subseteq TP1$ or $TP3 \subseteq TP2$ (Partial PArticipation, p-pa). Third, $TP1 = TP2$ (full participation, f-pa). If $TP1 \cap TP2 = \{\emptyset\}$, then there is no direct interaction, but there may be indirect interaction (Konidari and Mavrakis, 2006).

- iii) *Interactions due to rules-influencing mechanisms*. Two forms are encountered within this level, trading and regulative interaction (denoted by t and r, respectively). Two market-based PIs interact under t when rules for the same trading commodity (emission permit, green certificate, etc.) or market regulations of commodities of one instrument are affected due to the respective ones of the other (Konidari and Mavrakis, 2006). r is defined as interaction due to similar or same rules and influencing mechanisms of the two PIs regarding regulatory issues. These issues concern sanctions, subsidies, allocation procedures, counting and crediting (Konidari and Mavrakis, 2006).
- iv) *Interactions due to implementation network*. This interaction form occurs in the following cases. First, when the same competent authority has full responsibility for implementing both instruments; the form is named full responsibility interaction (f-r). Secondly, is the named partial responsibility interaction (p-r) when two or more authorities are assigned partial responsibilities for implementing both instruments. Third, different authorities are responsible for the equivalent number of different PIs and the form is named different responsibility interaction (d-r) (Konidari and Mavrakis, 2006).

Out of these four types of policy interactions the two first are more important. That is why the policy interaction analysis starts by the identification of the first type of policy interactions due to objectives and

continues with the second one. If two PIs interact under objectives and target groups, then there is strong policy interaction between them (Konidari and Mavrakakis, 2006).

Case studies

The selected for policy interaction analysis Hellenic case studies are:

- “Energy labelling” and “Green Public Procurement” (building and transport sector) – Direct link with energy;
- “Regulation for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings (KENAK)” and the “Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs” (Only for building sector) – Direct link with energy;
- “Planning policy instrument for Intelligent Transport Systems” and “Emission standards (Euro 5 and Euro 6)” (only for transport sector) – Indirect link with energy.

They were selected because of:

- the amount of available information about them compared to other national PIs (for all three cases).
- the significant market share that Greece has in the European solar market (for the second one).
- Their relation to energy efficiency (their outcomes support the promotion of energy efficiency practices and technologies) (for all three cases).

3. Policy interactions for the case studies

Policy interactions are explored under each of the aforementioned levels.

First level of policy interaction: Interaction due to objectives

1st case study: The Energy Labelling ⁸⁴ Directive aims to address the negative impacts of products on the environment depending on

how they are made, used and disposed of by 'pulling' the market towards more energy efficient products (European Commission, 2015). The objectives for fulfilling this aim are (European Commission, 2015): i) Increasing EE and the level of environmental protection; ii) informing consumers about EE and other resources use of products through an energy label, and encouraging them to buy more energy efficient ones; iii) Ensuring the free movement of energy-related products in the European Union.

For the Hellenic case, the Ministerial Decision 12400/1108/29 (Government Gazette 2301 B, 14.10.2011 ⁸⁵) sets as primary objective - in line with the aforementioned objectives of the Directive – to have end-users able to select more efficient products through an enacted framework for: i) providing information to end-users through labeling and ii) quoting uniform information regarding the product (energy consumption and occasionally other basic resources during usage) and supplementary information about products related with energy.

The purpose of the second PI, the EU Green Public Procurement (GPP), is to use the purchasing power of the EU Member States governments to stimulate the markets for goods and services with lower impacts on the environment (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013). Energy efficient products and services are promoted for use by the public sector.

The policy interaction is positive since both PIs through their objectives (primary and secondary) aim to support energy efficient products and services.

2nd case study: The objectives that KENAK serves are the: i) reduction of energy consumption for heating, cooling, lighting, production and use of hot water with the simultaneous ensuring of comfort conditions for the indoor spaces of buildings; ii) improvement of the energy performance of buildings in Greece, considering: a) outdoor

⁸⁴ and the Ecodesign Directive
⁸⁵

http://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&frm=1&source=web&cd=2&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CCKQFjABahUKEwjxv_GOz5HHAhUJORQKHdKrAX8&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ydmed.gov.gr%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2011_09_10_diminiaio.doc&ei=4tXBVfHGEonyUNLXhvgH&usq=AFOjCNFSqq8d5J aYRHwaeMdvBaHCMGeA8Q&bvm=bv.99261572.d.d

http://www.et.gr/ids-nph/search/pdfViewerForm.html?args=5C7QrtC22wFYAFdDx4L2G3dtvSoClrL8zS83ZvoDVVQtiDow6HITE-JInJ48_97uHrMts-zFzeyCiBSQOpYnTy36MacmUFCx2ppFvBej56Mmc8Qdb8ZfRjQZnsIAdk8Lv_e6czmhEembNmZCMxLMtZqO3PZEZmZ4PAm4MxQaM4YkkPuOjFkftnSx0GKTOsdy

climatic and local conditions and b) indoor climate requirements and cost-effectiveness.

The “*Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs*” was set in force by a Joint Ministerial Decision No. 12323⁸⁶ (Government Gazette 1079 B, 04.06.2009⁸⁷). Law 3851/2010 (Government Gazette 85 A, 04.06.2010⁸⁸) had relevant provisions with more important that for the feed-in-tariffs. Law 4023/2013 (Government Gazette 235 A, 11.11.2013⁸⁹) has also provisions that refer to PV systems on buildings. The objective of the “Specific Programme⁹⁰” is to contribute in the achievement of the national RES penetration target. It is the combination of two types of PIs: i) a regulatory PI due to the rules for the installation of the PV systems and ii) a financial PI due to the feed-in-tariffs for the Photovoltaic (PV) systems.

The target of total energy savings due to the installation of PV systems in the buildings sector for the production of domestic hot water use is estimated to 4.128 GWh until year 2020 (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013). The expected installed capacity of PV systems on lofts-roofs is expected to be by year 2020 at 1.150MW (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013).

The two PIs (KENAK and the regulatory part of the “Specific Programme”) interact positively through their common secondary objectives. The financial PI of the “Specific Programme” reinforces this type of policy interaction.

3rd case study: The objectives of Directive 2010/40/EC about the Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) are: i) establishment of the necessary specifications to ensure accessibility, exchange, reuse and update of road and traffic data for the provision of real-time traffic information services in the

European Union (European Commission, 2014). ii) Optimal use of road, traffic and travel data continuity of traffic and freight management ITS services; ITS road safety and security applications; linking of the vehicle with the transport infrastructure; facilitation of traffic management. Furthermore, according to this Directive, it is expected that the ITS application⁹¹ (to the road transport sector and its interfaces with other modes of transport) will contribute significantly to improved environmental performance, efficiency, including EE, safety and security of road transport, including the transport of dangerous goods, public security and passenger and freight mobility, ensuring also the functioning of the internal market and increasing the levels of competitiveness and employment.

The purpose of the emissions standards “Euro 5 and Euro 6” is to limit the pollution caused by road vehicles and support emission reduction actions in transport by introducing stricter limits on polluting emissions. These limits are applicable to light road vehicles, particularly with regard to emissions of particles and nitrogen oxides.

The two PIs share common secondary objectives which are the improvement of environmental performance (reduction of polluting emissions) and of EE (support of emission reduction actions). This results to positive policy interaction under objectives.

Second level of policy interaction: Interaction due to target groups

1st case study: The target groups of the Hellenic “Energy labeling” include end-users in households and producers of the respective products. This PI is applied to products that have significant effect (direct or indirect) on energy consumption and depending on the case of other resources during their use. It is not applied to: i) second hand products; ii) to

⁸⁶ <http://www.desmie.gr/ape-sithya/adeiodotiki-diadikasia-kodikopoiisi-nomothesia-ape/periechomena/timologisi-energeias-ape-ape/>

⁸⁷ http://www.cres.gr/pvcatalog/FEK_1079_2009.pdf or http://www.deddie.gr/Documents2/%CE%A6%CE%A9%CE%A4%CE%9F%CE%92%CE%9F%CE%9B%CE%A4%CE%91%CE%99%CE%9A%CE%91/eidiko%20programma%20steges/nomothesia/%CE%A6%CE%95%CE%9A%201079_4-6-2009.pdf

⁸⁸

<http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=pnhppGnURds%3D>

⁸⁹

<http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=6FFnUN2JqSg%3d&tabid=555&language=el-GR>

⁹⁰ The term “Specific Programme” refers to the *Specific Program for the Development of Photovoltaic systems on buildings and specifically on their lofts and roofs*

⁹¹ ITS applications should be without prejudice to matters concerning national security or necessary in the interest of defense.

transportation means of persons or merchandise; iii) on the indicative signal or the equivalent label for security reasons that is attached on the product.

For the GPP the target groups are public⁹² and private entities that sign contracts covering: energy efficient computers, office furniture from sustainable timber, low energy buildings, recycled paper, cleaning services using environmentally friendly cleaning products, electric, hybrid or low-emission vehicles, electricity from renewable energy sources (European Commission and ICLEI – Local governments for Sustainability, 2011).

There is no direct policy interaction under the target groups of the two PIs since they are different. For “*Energy Labelling*” the target group consists of end-users (citizens) coming from the building and the transport sectors, while for GPP the target groups are public entities. Producers and manufacturers of such products and services – whose participation is optional, particularly for the GPP - are benefitted indirectly by the implementation of both PIs. So, there is an indirect positive policy interaction.

2nd case study: *KENAK* is imposed on the following categories of buildings: i) Households of different types such as detached houses, apartments and apartment complexes; ii) Multi-apartment buildings; iii) Offices; iv) Educational buildings; v) Hospitals; vi) Hotels and restaurants; vii) Sports facilities; viii) Buildings for Wholesale and retail trade services; ix) Any other category of buildings that are consuming energy.

The “*Specific Programme*” concerns PV systems with power up to 10kW_p for buildings used as households or for housing small businesses. It will be in force until 31 December 2019 and covers the whole Hellenic territory. Natural persons that are non-traders and natural or legal persons that are traders (of very small businesses) can participate at the “*Specific Programme*” if they own a space at which they can install a PV system. The only condition is that there has to be an active connection for electricity consumption in the name of the PV owner at the building where the system is installed.

The two PIs interact directly between the target groups of the “*Specific Programme*” ie households of different types (ie detached houses, apartments and apartment complexes), multi-apartment buildings, offices, hotels – restaurants, buildings for wholesale and retail trade services and any other category of buildings that are consuming energy. It is a partial participation as described in the “policy interactions” session.

It is characterized as positive policy interaction based on the following justification. Despite the economic recession, the installation of PV systems on building roofs was significant (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013). The share of PV systems that were installed on roofs when compared to the whole Hellenic PV market demonstrated an increase from 4% in year 2010 to 19% during the first six months of year 2012 (Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013). This increase continued (Table 2). By April 2013, the installed capacity grew up to 341MW_p (HELAPCO, 2013).

Additionally, although photovoltaics are characterized as a relatively new technology for the Hellenic residential market, more than 40.000 systems were installed in residential buildings up to 2013, resulting to increased installed capacity (from 47 MW_p in 2007 to 1.536 MW_p in 2012 and to 2.579 MW_p in 2013) (Tsalikis G. and Martinopoulos G., 2015). Greece is among the ten top PV markets globally (10th in 2011 and 2012, 9th in 2013)(IEA, 2014).

3rd case study: The introduction and usage of ITS forms the following set of target groups: public authorities, private service providers (satellite links, internet, dedicated cable networks etc), road operators, private companies that develop and purchase the necessary equipment (traffic cameras, loop detectors), companies that own, elaborate and provide data and end-users (travelers, all categories of drivers (professional drivers, taxi drivers, drivers in public vehicles, elderly people etc)) (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015; European Commission, 2014; TISA, 2014).

⁹² Public sector, first and second level of local authorities, companies whose stock share belongs to the public sector or local authorities - Public transport sector

Under the emissions standards the target groups are: i) vehicle manufacturers and ii) owners of vehicles (categories⁹³ M1, M2, N1 and N2, with reference mass not exceeding 2.610 kg⁹⁴). These vehicles include, among others, passenger vehicles, vans and commercial vehicles intended for the carriage of passengers or goods or certain other specific uses (for example ambulances), provided that vehicles are equipped with engine-spark ignition (gasoline engines, engines with natural gas or Liquefied Petroleum Gas - LPG) or compression ignition (diesel engines).

The end-users (drivers of all vehicle types, private and public) are the common subset of the two target groups that benefit from the implementation of both PIs. Owners of vehicles with technology of Euro 5 and 6 when using ITS save travel time, consume less fuel and emit less. It is partial participation. No information is available for understanding if the number of end-users increased or remained the same due to the implementation of both PIs. The policy interaction is neutral.

Third type of policy interaction: Interactions due to rules - influencing mechanisms

1st case study: The Energy Labelling (or Eco-labelling) standards can be used as preconditions for the tenders of the GPP. So, the implementation of the GPP is facilitated while the implementation of the Energy Labelling standards is reinforced. The reasons are: i) energy or eco-labelling has a significant potential to contribute to an effective reduction of environmental impacts linked with economic activities due to its criteria which consider environmental impacts that products may have in their life-cycle (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015); ii) they inform consumers/users so as to select products energy efficient or least harmful to the environment because independent third parties narrow the information gap by assuring consumers/users about which product meets those energy or environmental standards (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015).

This is a positive “r” policy interaction between rules-influencing mechanisms of the two PIs.

2nd case study: Within the framework of the “*Regulation for the Energy Performance of Buildings (KENAK)*” and the provisions of Law 3851/2010⁹⁵ (Government Gazette 85 A, 04.06.2010⁹⁶), the use of RES in buildings and particularly the production of domestic hot water use by solar systems is obligatory for new buildings, while for totally renovated buildings the needs for hot water can be covered partially by solar thermal systems with the minimum percentage of annual solar share defined at 60% (YPEKA, 2014). This obligation is not applied for the uses that are exempted by the KENAK or when needs in domestic hot water use are covered by other decentralized energy supply systems based on RES, Combined Heat and Power (CHP), tele-heating systems (regionally or building block scale), heat pumps whose seasonal performance factor must be higher than 3,3 (YPEKA, 2014).

The Joint Ministerial Decision for the “*Specific Programme*” sets also the rule that “part of the thermal needs in domestic hot water use under the household of the PV owner needs to be covered by renewable energy sources (ie solar thermal systems and solar water heaters). The PV owner should not receive public financial support due to the Development-Investment Law or European financial mechanisms or any other funding resource so as to participate at the “*Specific Programme*” (Joint Ministerial Decision No. 12323).

Rules for the feed-in-tariffs, bills and payments are also defined. In 2010 the amount of the feed-in-tariffs was 550 EUR/MWh (Law 3851/2010). New adjustments followed. The feed-in-tariffs (financial policy instrument of the “*Specific Programme*”) were a strong incentive for the penetration of PV systems installed on lofts-roofs (HELAPCO, 2013). The target groups that fall under both PIs benefitted the most. Furthermore, the reduction of the average investment cost for PV systems with installed capacity up to 10kW_p was

⁹³ <http://www.dft.gov.uk/vca/vehicletype/definition-of-vehicle-categories.asp>

⁹⁴ defined in Annex II to Directive 70/156/EEC

⁹⁵ The law is about “Accelerating the RES development and confronting climate change - other provisions for issues under the responsibility of the MEECC

⁹⁶

<http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=pnhppGnURds%3D>

another significant factor for this penetration. The reduction was 64% comparing prices in year 2010 and 2013 (HELAPCO, 2013).

So, 3851/2010 (Government Gazette 85 A, 04.06.2010⁹⁷) which was devoted to the RES development linked RES and EE. The law formed a favorable context especially for photovoltaic installations on buildings, taking into consideration the very high prices for the generated electricity by these installations (550 EUR /MWh) when the maximum electricity price, for the household sector, for that period according to consumption ranged from 56,25 to 91,55 EUR /MWh (Christidou C. et al., 2014). PV investments under these conditions had pay-back periods shorter than six years (Christidou C. et al., 2014). This is positive “t” and “r” policy interactions between rules-influencing mechanisms of the two PIs.

3rd case study: Presidential Decree No. 50 (Government Gazette 100 A, 27.04.2012⁹⁸) incorporated Directive 2010/40/EU⁹⁹ (dated 7 July 2010) “on the framework for the deployment of Intelligent Transport Systems¹⁰⁰ in the field of road transport and for interfaces with other modes of transport” into national legislation, but the document presenting the “National Strategy for the Intelligent Transport Systems, 2015-2025” was released by the Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism only this year (March 2015) (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015). This document aims to identify shortages for the ITS, to present the relevant national needs and to define a set of required principles for the ITS implementation (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015). The document serves as a Roadmap for planning, implementing, operating and maintaining the ITS.

The Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (MEIST) (former

Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks) supports centrally the availability of real-time traffic data which are accessible by the private sector for a fee (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

There are emission limits for each category of pollutant emissions and for the different types of vehicles. According to provisions of EC Regulation 715/2007, the Member States shall lay down the provisions on penalties “applicable for infringement by manufacturers” according to their obligations under the Regulation. The respective penalties must be effective, proportionate and dissuasive. Offences subject to a penalty include: a) making false declarations during the approval procedures or procedures leading to a recall; b) falsifying test results for type approval or in-service conformity; c) withholding data or technical specifications which could lead to recall or withdrawal of type approval; d) use of defeat devices; and e) refusal to provide access to information.

There is no policy interaction under this category for the two PIs.

Fourth level of policy interactions: Interactions due to the implementation network/ governance structure

1st case study: The Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy¹⁰¹ (one of its former names was Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC¹⁰²)) monitors and supervises the implementation of measures for achieving the national indicative energy savings target through the provision of energy services and other measures to improve EE, and prepares a report on their results (2nd NEEAP, 2010; 3rd NEEAP, 2014). It has also the administrative, managing and executive responsibility of implementing the EE requirements of the “Energy Efficiency Action Plans” and relevant incentives and other

⁹⁷

<http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=pnhppGnURds%3D>

⁹⁸ www.yme.gr/getfile.php?id=4653

⁹⁹

<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:207:0001:0013:EN:PDF>

¹⁰⁰ Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) are advanced applications that integrate telecommunications, electronics and information technologies with transport engineering in order to plan, design, operate, maintain

and manage transport system. ITS provide innovative services relating to different modes of transport and traffic management and enable various users to be better informed and make safer, more coordinated and ‘smarter’ use of transport networks.

¹⁰¹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx>

¹⁰²

http://www.cres.gr/kape/calendar/progr_ypapen_8_6_15.pdf

measures to improve EE and those relating to the public sector.

MEECC is responsible for implementing the “*Energy labelling*”, and specifically, the General Secretariat of Industry at the Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former name also). The Public Economic Services, the Service of Special Audits of the Ministry of Finance, Hellenic Police, Chambers and Regions will also contribute for the market monitoring if the pertinent authority decides their involvement.

The MEECC was assigned also as the authority responsible to design the National Policy and to draw a National Action Plan for promoting the GPPs (Law 3855/2010 - Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010¹⁰³). MEECC will need to cooperate with other Ministries and bodies of the public and private sector for proceeding with the necessary legislative settings and measures for implementing the PI.

For the better coordination of these efforts an eleven member Interministerial Committee was established¹⁰⁴. Its Members are: The Minister of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (Head of Committee), The Minister of Finance, The Minister of Productive Reconstruction, Environment and Energy (Former MEECC), The Minister(s) who supervise(s) each of the Public Bodies that are examining the implementation of Public-Private-Procurements (PPP) projects, under their competencies.

There is a direct policy interaction (of full responsibility) since the MEECC is mainly responsible for implementing both PIs. This policy interaction can be characterized as negative due to lack of information about their implementation. This is justified as follows: i) There is still no national action plan about the GPP¹⁰⁵. Greece, along with Croatia, Estonia, Hungary, Luxemburg and Romania has not submitted such a plan. This situation imposes administrative burden to the implementation network. ii) there are no tenders with criteria related to Energy or eco-labelling or EE¹⁰⁶ on the Hellenic web-page for PPP due to inadequate implementation network (lack of

skills and knowledge to use the energy or eco-labelling standards under the GPP, lack of relevant studies, available perhaps but non-accessible information for the public through web-sites). This second reason is significant since public authorities are expected to be open and transparent about the management of public funds and assents (Domingues A.R. et al., 2015). The interaction can become positive if the necessary actions are undertaken (establishment of a pertinent authority with qualified staff etc).

2nd case study: The two main entities responsible for the implementation of both PIs are the MEECC and Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES)¹⁰⁷. CRES is the national centre for RES, Rational Use of Energy & Energy Saving. It is supervised by MEECC and has financial and administrative independence. It provides advice and assistance to MEECC on matters of RES/RUE/ES national policy, strategy and planning, is entitled to conduct dissemination and training campaigns as well as awareness raising campaigns on RES and ES. The main instruments used are, training activities, specialized events and production of material (technical guides, promotional publications, training software etc).

The support provided by CRES, particularly through studies, action plans and national reports, involves the fulfilment of national obligations under the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) and generally, under national and European legislation, relating to the EE of buildings, energy saving, renewable energy sources and cogeneration issues. CRES has a session on its web-site providing information (<http://www.cres.gr/services/istos.chtm?prnbr=24762&locale=el>) about a spectrum of issues related to EE (Buildings, transport, metering, GHG emissions, energy inspections/audits, certifications of materials and systems).

CRES has developed and completed a catalogue with institutes that are activated in RES and EE services and products. The purpose of this effort was to support the Hellenic market and to inform consumers and

¹⁰³

<http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=AxgQsUVAUjA%3d&tabid=506>

¹⁰⁴ <http://www.sdit.mnec.gr/en/information>

¹⁰⁵

http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/action_plan_en.htm

¹⁰⁶

<http://www.sdit.mnec.gr/en/information/PPP/procedures>

¹⁰⁷ <http://www.cres.gr/kape/index.htm>

investors about these types of market activities. The “Catalogue of Hellenic Energy Professionals” includes information about the type of activity of the involved companies and professionals, the category of RES, the relevant technology that is in use and contact data. However, there is no indication if this catalogue is updated (the date on the site is year 2007).

The type of policy interaction is not clear due to the lack of information. It can be characterized as neutral, since the performance of each policy instrument is not affected and the behavior of the end-users has not changed due to this implementation network.

3rd case study: The same authority is responsible for the implementation of both PIs, ie the Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (MEIST).

For the planning policy instrument of ITS, the pertinent national authority will be the Department of Planning and Development of Transport that is under the General Directorate of Transport of the Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015). This Department is assigned with the following responsibilities (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015):

- Implementation of the “National Strategy and Architecture for the ITS”. It is also responsible for the update and specialization of this strategy when these tasks are required;
- Installation of the implementation rules presented in national and European regulation documents for ITS;
- Monitoring of the progress for implementing the actions that derive

from the national and European regulation documents for ITS;

- Operation of the Advisory Committee¹⁰⁸ for ITS and of the ITS Observatory¹⁰⁹;
- Supervision of the registries with data required by the national and European regulation documents for ITS.

One more entity that is part of the implementation network for the ITS policy instruments is the Institute for the Management of Information Systems "Athena" which has developed and maintains the website www.geodata.gov.gr. It provides national support through a central point for collection, search, distribution and visualisation of information, e.g. bus routes (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

However, there is an overlap by entities such as Municipalities, OASA¹¹⁰ and the Egnatia Motorway in the performance of necessary actions (ie for implementing an integrated combined public information system for traffic, parking places and routes; informing public transport passengers etc) (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012). Defined roles and responsibilities for planning and coordination of such actions are not allocated clearly across the various levels of government (central government, local government) and transport operators (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

Other obstacles for the ITS implementation in the country are: i) Insufficient collaboration between public (central and regional) authorities and private entities; ii) lack of information for transport operators about the ITS and how they could implement them successfully, producing

penetration of the ITS applications. The ITS observatory is under the supervision of the Department of Planning and Development of Transport (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015).

¹¹⁰ The Athens Urban Transport Organization (OASA) is a metropolitan entity for urban transportation in Athens and was re-established with law 3920/2011 (OASA, 2012). For improving the polluted atmosphere of the greater's Athens area, OASA 110 replaced buses and trolley buses with new technology vehicles.

¹⁰⁸ The aforementioned Advisory Committee for ITS provides periodically or whenever that is necessary, consulting services to the Department of Planning and Development of Transport (Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015).

¹⁰⁹ The ITS Observatory records the ITS actions, evaluates them through appropriate indexes, the implementation outcomes and the ITS performance so as to draw objective conclusions for the progress of their implementation in Greece and the level of coordinated

benefits for enterprises (Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012).

For the second PI the Directorate “Vehicles Technology” of the MEIST is responsible for these issues. However, there are no available information about its implementation.

The current policy interaction is negative due to the overlap of responsibilities and the lack of clear responsibility distribution. The policy interaction can become positive if the aforementioned obstacles are confronted.

4. Conclusions

The outcomes are presented in table 1. The first case study has an overall positive policy interaction as discussed through the analysis in all four levels. The second case study is also an overall positive policy interaction situation, while the third one can be characterized as a neutral policy interaction.

The negative policy interaction is encountered under the fourth level – policy interactions due to implementation network/governance structure. Coordinated activities, defined and concrete responsibilities among the pertinent entities have the potential to increase the performance of the PIs.

Particularly, for the third case the two PIs will probably create a promising positive synergy, but empirical evidence to quantify this potential is not yet sufficient (European Commission, 2009). ITS for fuel consumption and/or emissions will allow monitoring and feedback so as to influence driving style and vehicle behavior (Ministry of Infrastructure, Transportation and Networks, 2014; European Commission, 2009).

The cases in which a positive policy interaction was identified can provide even more sufficient outcomes if the identified obstacles are confronted ie careful design of rules-influencing mechanisms and coordinated distribution of responsibilities for the entities that form the implementation network.

The establishment of authorities whose responsibilities are oriented exclusively to the achievement of the objectives of a specific PI and to the monitoring of its implementation will improve the current situation. From this point the presented approach can be used for understanding the performance of PIs and identifying their most effective combinations.

Table 1: Types of overall policy interactions for the three case studies.

Interaction due to	Case study		
	1	2	3
<i>Objectives</i>	Positive	Positive	Positive
<i>Target groups</i>	Positive	Positive	Neutral
<i>Rules-Influencing mechanisms</i>	Positive	Positive	Neutral
<i>Implementation network</i>	Negative	Neutral	Negative
Type of total policy interaction	Positive	Positive	Neutral

References

BIO Intelligence Service (2013), Implications of the new Energy Labelling Directive (2010/30/EU) and the Ecodesign of energy-related products (Ecodesign) Directive (2009/125/EC) on market surveillance activities, ATLETE II: Second Work Package prepared for. ADEME. Available at: <http://www.atlete.eu/2/doc/Report%20on%20implementation%20and%20national%20legislation> (Accessed: August 2015).

Build Up Skills – Energy Training for Builders, 2013. Build Up Skills – Greece, Analysis of the current situation at national level. Available at: [http://www.buildupskills.eu/sites/default/files/BUILD%20UP%20Skills-Greece>Status%20quo%20\(EL\)_0.pdf](http://www.buildupskills.eu/sites/default/files/BUILD%20UP%20Skills-Greece>Status%20quo%20(EL)_0.pdf) (Available only in Greek language) (Accessed: August 2015).

Christidou Chrysanthi, Tsagarakis Konstantinos P., Athanasiou Costas, 2014. Resource management in organized housing settlements, a case study at Kastoria Region, Greece. Energy and Buildings 74, pp. 17–29.

Domingues Ana Rita, Pires Sara Moreno, Caeiro Sandra, Ramos Tomas B., 2015. Defining criteria and indicators for a sustainability label of local public services. *Ecological Indicators* 57, pp. 452-464.

European Commission, 2009. The potential of Intelligent Transport Systems for reducing road transport related greenhouse gas emissions. Special study No. 2/2009. A Sectoral e-Business Watch study by SE Consult. Principal authors: Jian Bani, Vicente Lopez, Paloma Dapena. Madrid/Brussels. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/archives/e-business-watch/studies/special_topics/2009/documents/SR02-2009_ITS.pdf (Accessed: August 2015)

European Commission, 2014. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No.../.. of 18.12.2014. supplementing Directive 2010/40/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the provision of EU-wide real-time traffic information services (Text with EEA relevance). Available at: [http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/its/news/doc/2014-12-18-rtti/c\(2014\)9672_en.pdf](http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/its/news/doc/2014-12-18-rtti/c(2014)9672_en.pdf) (Accessed: August 2015).

European Commission, 2015. Commission Staff Working Document - Evaluation of the Energy Labelling and Ecodesign Directives Accompanying the document Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council on the review of Directive 2010/30/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the indication of labelling and standard product information of the consumption of energy and other resources by energy-related products - COM(2015) 345 final. Brussels, 15.7.2015 SWD(2015) 143 final. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/1_EN_autre_document_travail_service_part1_v2.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

European Commission and ICLEI – Local governments for Sustainability, 2011. Buying green! A handbook on green public procurement, 2nd edition. ISBN: 978-92-79-19930-1, doi: 10.2779/74936. Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/handbook.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015)

European Photovoltaics Industry Association, 2014. Global Market Outlook for Photovoltaics 2014–2018. Available at: http://helapco.gr/wp-content/uploads/EPIA_Global_Market_Outlook_for_Photovoltaics_2014-2018_Medium_Res.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

First Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2008. Pursuant to Directive 2006/32/EC. Prepared by the Ministry of Development and the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources in Athens, June 2008 (Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficiency-directive/national-energy-efficiency-action-plans> & http://uest.ntua.gr/archive/eupalinus/Sxedio_Drasis_Elladas_gia_EA_2006_32.pdf). Accessed on July 2015.

HELAPCO, 2013. Report about the PV installations of the Specific Program for the development of PV systems on roofs – May 2013. Available at: http://helapco.gr/pdf/Report_PV_Rooftop_100513.pdf (Available only on Greek language)(Accessed: August 2015).

Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, 2015. National Strategy for the Intelligent Transport Systems, 2015-2025. Available at: <http://www.yme.gr/?tid=1660> (Available only in Greek language)(Accessed: August 2015).

IEA, 2014. Trends 2014 in Photovoltaic Applications. Available at: http://helapco.gr/pdf/IEA_PVPS_Trends_2014_in_PV_Applications_-_lr.pdf, ISBN 978-3-906042-25-1 (Accessed: August 2015).

Konidari P. and Mavrakis D., 2006. Multi-criteria evaluation of climate policy interactions. *Journal of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis* 14, pp.35–53.

Mavrakis Dimitrios, Konidari Popi, 2003, “Classification of emission trading scheme design characteristics”, *European Environment* 13 (Wiley InterScience, ISSN: 0961-0405), pages 48-66

Ministry of Development, Competitiveness, Infrastructure, Transport and Networks, 2012. ITS Action Plan – The Action Plan for Intelligent Transport Systems in Greece. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/its/road/action_plan/doc/2012-greece-its-action-plan-2012-final_en.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

Ministry of Infrastructure, Transportation and Networks, 2014. Plan for the national strategy on ITS, October 2014. Available at: <https://www.dikaiologitika.gr/images/pdf/sxedio-esm.pdf> (Available in Greek language)(Accessed: August 2015).

OASA, 2012. Route towards sustainable development. Available at: <http://www.oasa.gr/pdf/el/annualreports/SR-14092012.pdf> (Available in Greek language)(Accessed: July 2015)

Second Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2008-2016, 2011. Pursuant to Directive 2006/32/EC. Prepared by the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources in Athens, September 2011. (Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficiency-directive/national-energy-efficiency-action-plans> & <http://www.buildup.eu/sites/default/files/content/EL%20-%20Energy%20Efficiency%20Action%20Plan%20EN.pdf>). Accessed on July 2015.

Third Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2014. – Pursuant to Article 24(2) of Directive 2012/27/EU. Prepared by the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources in Athens, December 2014. (Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/EL_NEEAP_en%20version.pdf). Accessed on July 2015.

Traveller Information Services Association (TISA), 2014. Terms and Definitions – Terms and Definitions for the Traffic and Travel Information Value Chain. Available at: <http://www.tisa.org/assets/Uploads/Public/EO12013TISADefinition-ITS-value-chain20121018.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

Tsalikis Georgios, Martinopoulos Georgios, 2015. Solar energy systems potential for nearly net zero energy residential buildings, *Solar Energy* 115 , pp. 743–756

YPEKA, 2014, Long Term Strategy report for the mobilization YPEKA, 2014, Long Term Strategy report for the mobilization of investments for the renovation of consisting of residential and commercial buildings, public and private, national building stock. (Article 4, Directive 27/2012/EU), Athens. Available at: <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=vDjk62bRxSI%3d&tabid=282&language=el-GR> (Available in Greek language) (Accessed: July 2015).